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D5.3: Report on demonstration at Demosite1: Lecce

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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Executive summary

Deliverables D5.3, D5.4, D5.5 and D5.6 describe the demonstration activities related to water treatment at the four demonstration sites in Italy, Israel, Spain, and Croatia respectively, performed in task T5.3 “Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules” in WP5 “Demonstration of small loops of water recycling within a complex system”.

Deliverable D5.3 reports the results of the demo activities at Project Ô Demosite1, performed in Lecce (Apulia Region, Italy). This deliverable builds on the content of D5.2 that describes the details of installation and validation of the ADV.ERT pilot plant for water treatment.

The present report includes:

- an introduction to the demonstration site and to the set of water treatment technologies included in the ADV.ERT water treatment module,
- the description of the general problem of the area under investigation: groundwater contamination in Apulia region,
- an overall description of demonstration activities undertaken,
- the results obtained during the demonstration activities.

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Abbreviations

AAU: Aalborg University

ADV.ERT: Advanced Tertiary Treatment

AQP: Acquedotto Pugliese S.p.A.

CFU: Colony Forming Unit

EKSO: Ekso S.r.l.

HiNaPEF: High Voltage Nano-Second Pulsed Electric Field

IRIS: IRIS S.r.l.

LOD: Limit of Detection

MPN: Most Probable Number

MW: Molecular Weight

NF: Nanofiltration

PAH: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

PEF: Pulsed Electric Field

P&I: Piping and Instrumentation diagram

SGN: Servizio Geologico Nazionale (Italian National Geological Service)

TOC: Total Organic Carbon

WWTP: Waste Water Treatment Plant

1 Introduction

The main objective of Project Ô is to develop and demonstrate a set of tools enabling circular use of water; among those tools there is a set of innovative technologies for water treatment characterized by high efficiency and low-cost processes, enabling the adoption of a modular approach.

This document collects the activities carried out in Task 5.3 (Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules: running of pilot plants with collection of data for monitoring) regarding Demosite1 in Lecce (Italy). The onsite demonstration and testing campaign was undertaken and resulted in the collection of operative data to evaluate the performance of the ADV.ERT module. A summary of the four demonstration sites is reported below:

Table 1 Brief summary of the four demonstration sites

Demosite 1: Acquedotto Pugliese, Lecce – Italy. Mobile desalination + advanced Oxidation Process for treating contaminated brackish groundwater.
Demosite 2: National Center for Mariculture, Eilat - Israel. Polishing algae plant for water reuse in RAS pond + disinfected fresh water for aquaponic produced through nano-pulsed PEF, membrane distillation and advanced adsorption treatments.
Demosite 3: Almendralejo WWTP, Almendralejo – Spain. Mobile Advanced Adsorption and Photo Fenton with advanced control unit
Demosite 4: Galeb, Omis – Croatia. Photocatalytic module and nanofiltration to allow water reuse in textile industry

The table below summarises key features of Demosite1, technologies and responsibilities for pilot scale module assembly and validation.

Table 2 Summary of the characteristics of Demosite1

Demosite1	Owner: AQP
ADV.ERT pilot plant	composed by: High-voltage nanosecond PEF (HiNaPEF by IRIS), nanofiltration (NF by AAU) integrated with contributions from EKSO (Leads: IRIS)
Purpose	desalination and disinfection of contaminated well water, obtaining water suitable for human consumption
Status	installed, validated, and fully operating. Demonstration activities at 24 m ³ /d, slightly higher than expectations

2 Demosite1: LECCE

2.1 Location

The demonstration site is located in Lecce, in Puglia Region, in Southeast Italy. The demonstration pilot was installed next to the Cozza-Guardati well (Figure 2 The gallery of Cozza-Guardati well) in Acquedotto Pugliese's (AQP) facilities.

Figure 1 Location of the demonstration site, in Apulia Region, SE Italy

Figure 2 The gallery of Cozza-Guardati well

2.2 The ADV.ERT module

The groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well is not compliant with the current drinking water regulations, therefore it cannot be used for human consumption without treatment. This water is microbiologically contaminated, and the source of the contamination is unknown (probably infiltration). Furthermore, Lecce is less than 10 km from the Adriatic Sea coast, and this causes saline intrusion, which raises the salinity of this water. To face these problems, the ADV.ERT pilot plant was designed to treat water onsite.

The plant is made of two modules: the Nanofiltration module (NF) and the HiNaPEF module. Those modules operate in synergy to tackle the main problems of the water from Cozza-Guardati well:

1. microbiological contamination: **High Voltage nano-second Pulsed Electric Field (HiNaPEF)** technology is able to abate the microbial charge in water matrices, using only electric field to perform the treatment (no chemical supply needed).
2. salinity: **Nanofiltration (NF)** uses innovative membranes, characterized by a distribution of pore sizes centred at the nanometre level, to remove salts and other pollutants (metals, organic contaminants, dissolved solids) from water matrices.

Figure 3 ADV.ERT module at the protected location of the demonstration site

3 Contaminated groundwater in Apulia Region

One of the main problems that need to be urgently tackled in the safeguard of the water resource in Apulia is the contamination of groundwater due to seawater intrusion, as outlined in many environmental reports, such as the SGN monograph¹.

Apulia is characterized by groundwater degradation determined mostly by the marine water intrusion in the continent. A comprehensive baseline of qualitative and quantitative data about the water quality in the groundwater network exists, a considerable number of detailed reports and multidisciplinary studies performed since the 1920s to date within various regional research projects. The volume I of publication no. 14 of the Central Hydrographic Service “The Italian springs” of the Apulian Region, published in 1928, started the detailed mapping of the surface water resources in the territory of the Hydrographic Compartment of Bari (extended for about 20,000 km²). After, analysis and flow measurements conducted in the period 1926-27 and measurements performed by the Hydrographic Section of Bari continued until the 1950s. The edition of volume 14 “The Italian Sources - List and description”, published in 1953, contained:

- a complete list of the 175 sources surveyed in total (comprising the 30 newly surveyed added to the original 145 already surveyed in the 1st edition), all with a flow rate of no less than 1 l/s, indicating the geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), the outflow section, the altitude above sea level, the flow rates and sometimes the outflow temperatures, measured starting from 1926;
- a concise outline of the main sources, characterized by a flow rate higher than 50 l/s;
- a map (at a scale of 1: 500,000), showing the location of the registered sources, distinguished according to the outflow rate (<10 l/s, between 10 and 50 l/s and > 50 l/s) and the census period.

After that, the quality of local groundwater was so degraded that it started to be replaced by other sources of water, mostly from neighbor regions.

Apulia represents one of the most interesting cases of the saltwater intrusion involving qualitative degradation of the freshwater resources stored in coastal karst aquifers in the Mediterranean area (Polemio, 2005; Polemio et al., 2009; De Filippis et al., 2016). Fabio Di Nunno and Francesco Granata² pointed out that currently the drinking water supply for 75% of the European population is provided by groundwater (Tulipano et al., 2005). Furthermore, quality aspects have to be taken into account when investigating the issue of water availability.

The average annual precipitation in Apulia is of approximately 600 mm. This data is lower than the average annual precipitation of Italy (about 1050 mm) and it is distributed mostly in winter, with storm events during the summer, as a characteristic of the Mediterranean climate (Fiorentino et al., 2013). In particular, Tavoliere area has the lowest annual rainfall values (400 mm), whilst Gargano area registers the highest values (1100–1200 mm).

In addition, the karst environments, formed from the dissolution of soluble rocks such as limestone and dolomite widespread in the region, is characterized by the water rapidly infiltrating within the epikarst through the network of cavities and conduits (Parise, 2003). As an effect, there is a shortage availability of surface waters, increasing the uncontrolled exploitation of groundwater for irrigation, and this enhances the saltwater intrusion. The local economy is significantly impacted by these phenomena, due to the fact that the 72% of the land of this region is for agricultural use and the 75% of the water resources for irrigation use is offered by the groundwater (De Giglio et al., 2019). In addition, a leading cause of the groundwater depletion is related to the irrigation water demand (Dong et al., 2019).

A comprehensive description of geographical and hydrogeological features of Apulia can be retrieved in the study “Microbiological and hydrogeological assessment of groundwater in southern Italy”

¹ SGN, Technical Periodicals, Memorie Descrittive della Carta geologica d'Italia, Vol. 92/2014, ISBN: 978-88-9311-003-7

² “Groundwater level prediction in Apulia region (Southern Italy) using NARX neural network” (Environmental Research, Volume 190, 2020, 110062, ISSN 0013-9351)

(Environmental Monitoring Assessment (2016)³), which covers 19,358 km² and has 4 million inhabitants, mostly engaged in agriculture, tourism, and livestock rearing.

Apulia spans about 350 km in southeast Italy, between the Adriatic and Ionian Seas, with extensive coastal development along its 800 km coastline and a typical Mediterranean climate, with mild dry winters and hot summers. The geographical, climatic, and geological conditions (a mostly karst-fissured landscape) of this region make it lack significant surface water, with the exception of the Ofanto and Fortore Rivers (in the northeast of the region), whilst the other rivers are short and ephemeral, and the natural lakes are few and distributed along the coast. The largest source of groundwater recharge is rainfall, which is highly irregular throughout the year.

In this context, technologies enabling onsite treatment of polluted water sources have a massive potential. The objective in Demosite1 is providing a mobile water treatment module for addressing contamination of groundwater from artesian wells bored in the karstic aquifers, that provide about 99.5% of the groundwater in the Apulian region, to exploit them as sources of safe drinking water, thus easing the pressures on the aqueduct providing high quality water from alternative sources.

³ 188: 638DOI 10.1007/s10661-016-5655-y

4 Demonstration activities

WP5 is directed to show the tools that allow water management in small loops, in terms of advanced technologies and impact evaluation tools: this also includes the demonstration activities reported in this deliverable. Whilst D5.2 reported the site preparation, the installation of the pilot plants and their operation, this document instead focuses on the demonstration activities and data collection at Demosite1.

ADV.ERT module at Demosite1 is integrated in a container, designed to be moved where needed. The layout of the module is described in detail in D5.2. The purpose of the module is the treatment of contaminated groundwater to drinking water quality.

Figure 4 The ADV.ERT pilot plant in Lecce

Key characteristics of contaminated groundwater are summarised in Table 3 Main characteristics of contaminated groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well in Lecce, Demosite1) together with the target value after the ADV.ERT treatment.

Table 3 Main characteristics of contaminated groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well in Lecce, Demosite1

Key variable	Units	Untreated groundwater ⁴	Target value	Limits (Italian law for drinking water) ⁵
E. coli	CFU/100 ml	222	0 CFU/100 ml ⁶	0 CFU/100 ml
Coliform bacteria at 37° C	CFU/100ml	306	0 CFU/100 ml	0 CFU/100 ml
Colony count at 22°C	CFU/ml	230	No relevant fluctuations	no relevant fluctuations. it is not necessary to monitor this parameter for water supplies lower than 10000m ³ /day
Conductivity	µS/cm at 20°C	1123	<2500	<2500

⁴ Average values

⁵ D.Lgs 31/01

⁶ D.Lgs 31/01

The demonstration activities took place in Lecce, at AQP facilities. The first part of demonstration activities involved the optimization of process parameters to achieve the best treatment. In order to minimise time and costs, IRIS set up a testing and optimization station in Orbassano (IRIS' facilities) to perform remote assistance, troubleshooting, and part of the optimization of process parameters of the ADV.ERT module. This allowed to considerably speed up the operations.

The station at IRIS was comprising of the HiNaPEF and NF technologies, mirroring the technologies in Lecce, and of a testing station for microbiological analysis, since microbiological contamination was the most delicate parameter to optimise at the demonstration site.

Figure 5 NF module at IRIS

Figure 6 Testing station at IRIS

5 Testing report

5.1 Testing campaign description

The testing campaign was set-up to establish if the ADV.ERT module is correctly operating:

- in relation to the specification drawn in D5.1
- in relation to the current Italian legislation on water quality

In D5.2 we described the installation and the validation procedures of the ADV.ERT module. Here we'll describe the subsequent testing campaign. We decided to take one sample every week since the module validation at the beginning of July to monitor water input/output. The physicochemical and microbiological analysis were conducted by "Laboratorio Multisito Acquedotto Pugliese" (at their Bari and Lecce facilities). Following the recommendation of D2.1, since this water comes from a well-mixed source (no peaks or throughs in flow), we decided to "grab sample". As we'll see, the analyses confirm that the Cozza-Guardati groundwater contaminants' concentrations are rather stable over time. The samples were collected at the first available tap of the ADV.ERT module, in HDPE containers for metal analyses (then kept in the dark at 4°C) and in glass containers (flame sealed, then stored in the dark) for microbiological analyses. The microbiological analyses, conducted under the supervision of the head of "Area Controllo Igienico Sanitario" (that'd translate as "Hygienic and Sanitary Control") Dott. Paolo Saracino were performed on the same day of the sampling to ensure preservation and to cope with the "less than 30 hours" recommendation of D2.1. Samples were labelled with an alphanumeric string that enables to recover location, date and sample number. For every sample an identification sheet was drawn.

5.2 ADV.ERT monitoring system

The ADV.ERT module is equipped with sensors to monitor operation, a PLC with logging capabilities and with a 4G modem that enables remote operation or data retrieval. In the previous D5.2 deliverable, we've reported the piping and the position of every sensor. Here we recall and integrate that discussion to provide the necessary information needed to follow through the next section, in which we'll report the data from the sensors.

Figure 7 ADV.ERT P&I diagram

Sensors and transducers description:

Flow measurements

FIT1, FIT2, FIT3 and FIT4 are flow transducers:

1. FIT1 measures the flow from TK1 to the membranes
2. FIT2 measures the retentate flow
3. FIT3 measures the flow from PC3, the well pump
4. FIT4 measures the flow from TK1 to the HiNaPEF module

FI1 is a visual flow meter on the permeate outlet.

Pressure measurements

PT1, PT2, PT3, PT4 and PT5 are pressure transducers:

1. PT1 measures the pressure reached by the pre-charge pump PC3
2. PT2 measures the pressure downstream the safety filter (F1)
3. PT3 measures the pressure reached by the high-pressure pump PC2
4. PT4 measures the retentate pressure
5. PT5 measures the permeate pressure

PI1 and PI2 are visual pressure gauges.

Conductivity measurements

CIT1, CIT2 and CIT are conductivity transducers:

1. CIT1 measures the permeate conductivity
2. CIT2 measures the retentate conductivity
3. CIT3 measures the conductivity of the water upstream the HiNaPEF module

pH1 is a pH transducer downstream the HiNaPEF module and TT1 is the water feed to the membrane temperature.

5.3 Analysis of collected data

In this section are reported sensors' data retrieved from the ADV.ERT module, gathered during the testing campaign. It's important to notice that the module records the sensors' signals every 10 minutes, generating a conspicuous amount of data during its operation. To streamline the discussion here we report the averages, calculated from a substantial dataset, for the first 10 days of the testing campaign. It should be noted that, as can be inferred from Figure 10 Flow data from NF unit, the first four days of the testing campaign were used to find the optimal operative conditions for the nanofiltration unit.

Temperature data from TT1 Temperature Transducer:

Figure 8 Temperature of the groundwater feed - averages for the first 10 days of activities

The temperature of the groundwater feed is rather stable, with minimal fluctuation due to the intrinsic seasonality.

Figure 9 pH of the groundwater feed – averages from the first 10 days of activities

As can be confirmed from the physicochemical analysis reported further in this document, the chemical composition doesn't largely over time, reflecting in a stable pH value.

Figure 10 Flow data from NF unit – averages from the first 10 days of activities

In Figure 10 Flow data from NF unit) we report data from the nanofiltration unit flow transducers. The membrane feed data come from FT1 while the permeate flow can be calculated subtracting the retentate flow (FT2) from the membrane feed (FT1).

Figure 11 NF operative pressures – averages from the first 10 days of activities

In the graph Figure 11 NF operative pressures) we show data for the permeate pressure (PT2), high pressure membrane feed (PT3) and the retentate pressure (PT4). From this and the previous graph in Figure 10 Flow data from NF unit), the status of the membrane can be inferred (to eventually detect fouling).

Figure 12 Water conductivity – averages from the first 10 days of activities

The most significant data that can be gathered by the ADV.ERT module control are the water conductivities. In Figure 12 Water conductivity) we report the conductivity data for the ADV.ERT module. The feed transducer (CIT3) gives the conductivity of the untreated water feed from the well. CIT2 yields the retentate conductivity while the permeate conductivity is given by CIT1. These data, combined with the pressures and the flows, can clearly help in finding the optimal operative conditions or a membrane degradation (fouling).

In addition to data collected from sensors, periodical water analysis was performed to control the values of more than 170 parameters.

Water can be an ideal habitat for bacterial growth due to the presence of nutrients and oxygen, the main contamination issue in groundwater from the demonstration site in Lecce is the presence of bacteria in relevant concentrations.

According to the Italian regulation, drinking water (a) must have zero coliforms and (b) the variations in the total bacterial count must be as small as possible. The microbiological analysis of the groundwater was performed before and after the treatment; the analysis targeted specific indicators and bacterial strains, as indicated in the drinking water regulation and guidelines.

Bacteria commonly related to health risks include:

- Coliform Bacteria. The presence of coliforms in water can cause gastrointestinal disease. Coliform bacteria were found in relevant amounts in the untreated groundwater, their presence can be explained by contamination from unauthorized discharge of urban waste and black water in the surrounding area.
- Escherichia Coli. E. Coli is one of the most known coliforms, and it is linked to fecal contamination, being present in human intestine.
- Enterococci. Like coliforms, enterococci are present in human and animal intestine, enterococci are generally more resistant to disinfection than coliforms. Presence of enterococci is related to fecal contamination.
- Clostridium perfringens. This spore is related to the recent contamination of water. No clostridium perfringens was detected in the water at the demonstration site.

*Figure 13 Bacteria in water, before and after treatment with ADV.ERT module.
 Analysis according to Italian regulation for drinking water.
 Total coliforms are measured in MPN/100ml; the other parameters are measured in CFU/100ml.*

The value of “Total Coliforms” indicator for the input water from Demosite1 ranges from 30 to 200 MPN/100ml. MPN is an analytical procedure (MPN stands for “Most Probable Number”) that searches for specific microorganisms that indicate the presence of pathogens in water; those indicator microorganisms include fecal coliforms and streptococci, according to the Italian normative for water analysis. Enterococci and E. Coli in input water range from 2 to 20 CFU/100ml. CFU stands for “Colony Forming Units”.

The number of coliforms, E. Coli and enterococci in untreated water is considerably higher than the limits for drinking water. After the treatment with the ADV.ERT module the values approach zero (values are below the detection limit).

Another important microbiologic parameter is the “Total Colony Count”, which takes into account non-fecal bacteria. Any bacteria present in the water is incubated at 22°C or 36°C for a set amount of time before they are counted. The Italian regulation doesn’t set a limit to the number of colonies, any value is acceptable as long as there aren’t any abnormal changes in time (relevant changes in time could indicate that the disinfection system is damaged or malfunctioning).

The total amount of bacteria in input water (before the treatment) ranges from 50 to 160 UFC/ml and it is always reduced after the treatment. The percentage of reduction depends on the type of colony count (performed at 22°C or 36°C) and the results in output are consistent in time, not showing any abnormal variation.

Figure 14 Colony count in groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well before and after treatment with ADV.ERT module. Values in the graph refer to the worst case encountered during the demonstration period

It can be concluded that the microbiological contamination at Demosite1 was successfully addressed by the ADV.ERT technologies.

The second major issue with the groundwater from the demonstration site is related to seawater intrusion, that results in high water conductivity. During the demonstration period the conductivity of water was below the legal limit for drinking water, ranging between 1.15 and 1.9 mS/cm; however, the ideal value should be less than 1 mS/cm. High conductivity is not a concern for human health, but it has a huge impact on the satisfaction of clients, and it may cause water hardness and alkalinity.

Figure 15 Decrease in water conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and hardness (French Degrees) after treatment with ADV.ERT module.

The decrease in water conductivity after the treatment is substantial, as well as the decrease in hardness. Conductivity goes from about 1200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to about 500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Since this is an important indicator of the correct behavior of the ADV.ERT treatment module, online monitoring of water conductivity was implemented, as described in chapter 5.2.

To determine the water quality, other relevant parameters are TOC and Fixed Residue. The TOC is the measure of the total organic carbon in water, including dissolved and non-dissolved carbon. The organic matter can have a natural origin or be present as a consequence of anthropic activities. The organic matter in water isn't necessarily toxic but high values can impact the ecosystem (e.g., by depleting oxygen levels in water) and can be detrimental for the organoleptic quality of water impacting odor, taste and color.

Even though the TOC value in groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well is below the upper limit for drinking water, the comparison of TOC values before and after treatment is very useful because a decrease in TOC indicates higher water quality.

Knowing the typical TOC value in input water is also useful to optimize the disinfection treatment to avoid inefficiencies: the disinfection treatment cannot discriminate between harmful microorganisms and harmless organic matter; therefore, high values of TOC can decrease the efficiency of most disinfection systems. The TOC values from Demosite1 untreated water are low and don't interfere with the HiNaPEF treatment, as can be expected in groundwater.

Figure 16 TOC values in water before and after ADV.ERT treatment.

After the ADV.ERT treatment, the TOC is less than half, indicating a significant increase in water quality.

Figure 17 Fixed residue at 180°C in water, before and after ADV.ERT treatment

Other relevant parameters include fixed residue, which is the precipitate remaining after the evaporation of 1 liter of water at 180°C, expressed in mg/l. The higher the content of mineral salts dissolved in the water, the greater the weight of the residue obtained. Both before and after the treatment, the water can be classified as mineralized water, with a good tenor of salts, comparable with slightly mineralized bottled water.

Water alkalinity is basically the acid neutralizing capabilities of water, and it is commonly measured in amount of CaCO₃ or HCO₃. The quantity of carbonates and bicarbonates in treated water is lower than it was in untreated water, as expected after a nanofiltration treatment. The pH of water, both before and after the treatment, ranges between 6.5 and 7.5, which is considered a good value for drinking water.

Figure 18 Water hardness before and after the ADV.ERT treatment

It is interesting to explore the different behavior of mono- and bi-valent ions in water treated with a nanofiltration system. Nanofiltration treatment uses membranes with intermediate properties between porous and non-porous: the separation mechanism is quite complex, and it includes both mechanical separation (sieving, dimensional exclusion) and diffusion transport (electrostatic interactions).

The first mechanism is evident for neutral molecules (typical threshold is MW 200) while the salt rejection mechanism is mainly due to “Donnan effect” and it is more effective with polyvalent ions. For this reason, the retention of monovalent ions with nanofiltration is usually very small. This behaviour is confirmed by the water analysis performed as shown in Figure 19 Concentration of selected monovalent ions before and after the ADV.ERT treatment.

Figure 19 Concentration of selected monovalent ions before and after the ADV.ERT treatment.

Figure 20 Concentration of selected bivalent ions before and after the ADV.ERT treatment.

This is evident when looking at the results of concentration of monovalent and bivalent ions in the output flow: the concentration on monovalent ions such as sodium and potassium is almost the same before and after the ADV.ERT treatment. On the other hand, the concentration of bivalent ions, such as sulfate and manganese, greatly decreases after the treatment.

Iron is abundant on the surface of the Earth; therefore, it is naturally found in groundwater as ferrous and ferric iron. The presence of iron in the groundwater from the Cozza-Guardati well is unlikely to be related to anthropic activities because of the absence of relevant industries manufacturing iron or ferrous compounds. In general, the presence of iron in water is not dangerous, however it can alter the organoleptic properties of water and can lead to the corrosion of the water distribution network.

Iron in surface water often precipitates naturally, while it can be found in groundwater due to the anaerobic conditions. The reduction in the content of iron after the treatment is probably due to a combination of factors including the aeration of water in the input tanks of the plant, the oxidation and the filtration treatments in the ADV.ERT system.

Figure 21 Iron in groundwater before and after the treatment with ADV.ERT module

The total amount of iron in the groundwater at the demonstration site is well below the legal limits for drinking water, after the treatment the value is so low that it is not detectable (LOD = 1µg/l).

Nitrates (NO₃⁻) are commonly found in groundwater, particularly in rural areas since they are related to the use of fertilizers containing nitrogen. An excessive quantity of nitrates can be harmful itself, especially to babies since their digestive system is unable to process nitrates. Additionally, the presence of nitrates can also indicate the incidence of other pollutants related to agriculture, such as pesticides.

Usually, the concentration of nitrates in water is considered ideal when about 15 mg/l. The Italian regulation, in accordance with WHO guidelines, suggests as 50 mg/l as upper threshold, but up to 100 mg/l is considered acceptable.

Figure 22 Nitrates in groundwater before and after the treatment with ADV.ERT module

The quantity of nitrates in Lecce's groundwater before the ADV.ERT treatment is acceptable, typically slightly below 50 mg/l, it further decreases after the treatment with the ADV.ERT module: the value of nitrates after the treatment is around 30 mg/l.

Nitrites were not detected in the water from the Cozza-Guardati well.

The input groundwater was periodically tested for the presence of a wide range of pesticides and antiparasitics as well as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH); none of these compounds was detected in the groundwater.

Many additional elements were tested in the input water, both elements that are present in certain soils (such as arsenic) and elements that typically have anthropic origin (such as vanadium); none of those was found in relevant amount. The complete list of compounds investigated is reported in Annex I – Complete list of biological, physical, and chemical parameters investigated.

The output water from the ADV.ERT module installed in Lecce complies with the Italian and European water regulations.

5.4 Water quality over time

In the following paragraphs it is reported the behaviour over time of the main parameters indicating the quality of water after the ADV.ERT treatment module.

The samples for the analysis were collected from a fountain placed at the demonstration site. The fountain was fed the output water from the ADV.ERT module since July. It is clearly visible the increase in water quality: since July, water conductivity is always below 530 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and, since the end of July, harmful bacteria dropped to zero.

Looking at the data from the beginning of July, it can be observed that the quantity of coliforms was considerably reduced, but not zero. Further improvements of process parameters allowed to reach zero coliforms in water.

Figure 23 Fountain connected to the output of the ADV.ERT treatment module

Figure 24 Coliforms in water from the fountain in Lecce, connected to the ADV.ERT treatment module since July 2022

Figure 25 Water conductivity from the fountain in Lecce, connected to the ADV.ERT treatment module since July 2022

Considering the performance per cubic meter of water treated, the electric energy consumption is 0.36 kWh/m³ for HiNaPEF and 2.2 kWh/m³ for NF. The low energy consumption allows for considering the objectives of the project achieved. In the future, further improvements in energy consumed can be made: the efficiency of the generator of the HiNaPEF can be further improved, the operative pressure of the NF can be further reduced by improving the performance of the membranes. Energy consumed by pumps, controls and sensors is included in the calculations. The ADV.ERT module is designed to allow integration with photovoltaic panels, to enable its use in remote areas as well as in emergency situations.

6 Conclusions

Demosite1 is the only site in project Ô that is expected to produce drinking quality water. For this reason, very thorough analysis was performed at regular intervals and matched with data from sensors, the complete list of parameters analysed is available in Annex1.

Overall, the quality of output water is very good and stable in time. The water is compliant with national and European regulations for drinking water, exceeding the required quality in regard to many parameters. In conclusion, the technologies in the ADV.ERT module are effective and low-cost and allow for onsite treatment of contaminated groundwater achieving drinking quality water.

Figure 26 Experts from IRIS, AQP and UNITO working at the ADV.ERT module at Demosite1, details of the technologies inside the ADV.ERT module

Annex I – Complete list of biological, physical, and chemical parameters investigated

Benzene
Vinyl chloride
1,2 dicloroethane
Trihalomethanes (THM)-totali
Cloroform
Bromoform
Dibromocloroethane
Bromodicloromethane
Trihalomethanes totali
Tetracloroethylene
Trichlorethylene
Tetra-trichlorethylene tot.
Epichlorohydrin*
Turbidity
TOC
Temperature*
Fixed residue at 180°C
Alcalinity*
Bicarbonate*
Oxidizability*
free residual chlorine *
Litium*
total residual chlorine *
Potassium*
Beryllium*
Cobalt*
Tin*
Bromides*
Bromate
Nitrite
Aluminum
Ammonium*
Antimony
Arsenic
Barium
Borum
Cadmium
Calcium
Chlorate
Chlorite
Conductivity
Chrome
Hardness
Iron
Fluoride

Magnesium
Manganese
Mercury
Nichel
pH
pH
Measured temperature
Lead
Copper
Selenium
Sulphate
Vanadium
Zinc
Color*
Odour*
Taste*
Sodium
Cianuri*
Nitrate
Cloride
Pesticides Tot*
Alaclor*
Atrazine-desethyl*
Atrazine-desisopropyl*
Benfluralin*
Bromacil*
Carbetamide*
Chlorpyriphos*
Chlorpyriphos-methyl*
Cyanazina*
Diazinon*
Dichlobenil*
Dicloran*
Dimethenamid*
Disulfaton*
Endosulfan alfa*
Endosulfan beta*
Endosulfan solfato*
Endrin*
Endrin aldehyde*
Endrin ketone*
Ethofumesate*
Famphur*
Fenitrothion*
HCl alfa Lindane*
HCl beta Lindane*
HCl delta Lindane*
HCl gamma Lindane*
Linuron*

Metazachlor*
Mcthoxychlor*
Metolachlor*
Mirex*
Molinate*
Oxyfluorfen*
Parahion ethyl*
Parahion methyl*
Penconazole*
Pendimethalin*
Phorate*
Pirimicarb*
p,p DDD*
p,p DDE*
p,p DDT*
Prometryn*
Propachlor*
Propazine*
Simazine*
Sulfotepp*
Terbutryn*
Terbutylazina*
Tetrachlorvinphos*
Tetradifon*
Thionazin*
Trifluralin*
Vemolate*
Vinclozolin"
0,0,0-Trimethylphosphorotionate
2,6-Diclorobenzamide*
Pesticides tot. (70 analytes)*
TOT pesticides
Aldrin
Atrazine
Bromopropilato
Desetilterbutilazina
Dicldrin
Dimetoato
Eptacloro
Eptacloro epossido
Esaclorobenzenc
rsodrin
Pentaclorobenzene
1,2,3,4,-Tetraclorobenzene
pesticides Tot (12 analytes)
PAH*
Benzo[a]Anthracene*
benzo[j]fluoranthene*
Chryscne*

Dibenz[a,h]anthracene*
Naphthalene, 1-methyl*
Naphthalene, 2-methyl*
Perylene*
Pyrene*
PAH tot (20 analytes)*
PAH
Acenaphthene
Acenaphthylene
Anthracene
benzo[a]pyrene
benzo[b]fluoranthene
benzo[g,h,i]perylene
benzo[k]fluoranthene
Fluoranthene
Fluorene
indeno[1,2,3-c,d]pyrene
Naphthalene
Phenanthracene
Tot PAH (normate)
Tot PAH (12 analytes)
Coliforms a 37°C
Enterococcus
Escherichia coli (E. coli)
Clostridium perfringens*
Colony count at 22°C *
Colony count at 36°C *

* Analysis according to Italian standard drinking water analysis procedure